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Psychological preparation for physical and competitive conditions

Utegov Makhmud Daurkhanovich

*Teacher of the Department of Theory and Methodology
physical culture of Karakalpak state university*

Abstract. *Psychology, sports training is important for an athlete to consider. In order to achieve maximum results in sports, it is necessary to work hard not only for training, but also to pay great attention to moral and psychological training.*

Keywords: *moral training, endurance, athlete's patience,, competition, psychology training..*

Introduction

To become a successful athlete, you need to pay attention to all the components of successful athletic activity, both mental and physical. Since an athlete does not enter a competition with a completely empty head, he needs to include psychological training in the training program. This will allow him to develop strategies that will prepare him to participate in competitions with the "right mindset."

If an athlete is interested in getting the most out of their athletic efforts, they need to consider their performances as a combination of individual factors. An athlete would never think about participating in a competition without taking the time to physically prepare their body, but nevertheless, most athletes compete without analyzing what psychological skills they will need to achieve the best physical performance.

As sports sciences develop, it becomes increasingly important to integrate mental and physical aspects. Traditionally, cognitive aspects have not been given due attention. Coaches and athletes pay more attention to physical components.

However, both the coach and the athletes often associate the failure to achieve athletic results with psychological aspects, such as "he wasn't concentrating," "he was tense," "she couldn't handle the stress of the competition," "I was so scared..." and others. All these comments are often used to describe the frustrations of competition, but it is rare to find a coach who says that an athlete has not been taught the right psychological skills and strategies.

An athlete rarely realizes that the failure was due to poor or ineffective psychological preparation. After the competition, the highest percentage of excuses is usually associated with psychological and emotional aspects. However, almost no time is spent on including them in the training program. Rather, there is an increase in training time. It should be noted that there are no noticeable changes in the athlete's physical abilities during the competition or between two competitions that follow each other directly. An athlete does not suddenly lose stamina, talent, skills, or speed in a day, week, month, or sometimes even years. What affects him is psychological control or thinking. An athlete can gain or lose psychological control, or lose his temper in just a split second.

These psychological fluctuations can be prevented by developing cognitive skills and strategies to manage anxiety, stress, negative thoughts and emotions. Sometimes athletes blame the coach, parents, fans, or even the weather when something goes wrong or if they don't reach their full potential. But the effectiveness depends on the psychological attitude of the athlete.

Discussion. Moments of panic, anxiety, and emotional ups and downs can affect physical performance at any level. Athletes who continue to perform with some degree of consistency, despite feeling anxious, have learned to deal with it in one way or another. However, relatively few of them were trained in skills and strategies that would allow them to cope with stress. Athletes are helped to develop their physical skills, but few have tried to help them develop the necessary psychological qualities.

Many people believe that having someone to teach an athlete psychological skills means that the athlete is unstable, has "mental problems" or is "completely insane." There is an opinion among coaches and even some athletes that psychologists are people who help those who are worried or ill-adjusted. They believe that a "normal" athlete does not need help from a person who has undergone psychological training and, in particular, sports psychology. Besides, many coaches only need hard-thinking athletes.

No one can dispute the fact that mental state largely depends on productivity. However, almost nothing has been done to identify the emotional and or mental factors that hinder good performance, as well as attempts to identify those factors that lead to poor performance. Basically, what sports psychology does for an athlete is to teach an athlete to identify the factors that lead to good results and the factors that lead to bad results. This provides a basis for understanding why an athlete shows good or inconsistent results. The human body is a very complex whole consisting of many different, but at the same time highly integrated biological systems that promote effective interaction between the internal and external environment. These very different systems are integrated and controlled by the nervous system. Some nerve endings specialize in vision, smell, touch, temperature, pain, and others, but the entire nervous system coordinates the body's responses to the internal and external environment. In sports, as in all other situations, there is a combination of different reactions. Some of these reactions occur on a conscious level, while others occur on a subconscious level.

The logic is that muscles don't function unless the brain tells them to. A person does not perform physical exercises in isolation without mental abilities. Athletic performance should be approached from a holistic perspective in order to combine "thinking with muscles" to achieve high levels of performance. There is also a reverse reaction: the mental state largely depends on physical performance. Everyone knows that anxiety and negative emotions about work can lead to decreased productivity. One way to avoid this is through comprehensive coaching and training. The vast majority of famous athletes are aware of the

importance of psychological preparation for competitions. Athletic performance is 90% mental, and many great athletes also believe that psychological preparation is crucial to determining results. That is, when athletes have developed their physical skills to a high level and when they compete at that level, the winner is more likely to be the person who is best prepared psychologically.

Coaches also recognize the importance of psychological training, but coaches may neglect sports psychology, most likely because they do not know how to teach athletes basic psychological skills. There are also coaches who are of the opinion that

Psychosocial qualities are innate characteristics that cannot be taught;

Athletes either have these psychological qualities or they don't;

Psychological preparation is not important and only hard physical work is needed to prepare athletes.

But, nevertheless, currently the vast majority of coaches are aware of the importance of psychological training, but simply do not know how to implement it.

It should be emphasized that regular practice of psychological skills is necessary, and after all psychological skills are mastered, they can be applied during competitions. As athletes begin to acquire these skills, most of them don't even realize it.

The result. At the same time, psychological training should be short compared to physical training, but regular.

Let's consider how sports psychology can help.:

1. Improve concentration and get rid of distractions. Many athletes have the ability to concentrate, but often their attention does not shift to the right areas.
2. Increase confidence in doubting athletes. Doubt is the opposite of certainty. If an athlete retains doubts before or during the competition, it indicates low self-confidence, or at least he is sabotaging the confidence that you had at the beginning of the competition.
3. Develop coping skills with failures and mistakes. Emotional control is a necessary condition. It is difficult for athletes with very high expectations to correct minor mistakes, which are a natural part of sports. It's important to meet these expectations, as well as help athletes stay calm under pressure when they make mistakes or get upset.
4. Helps sports teams develop communication skills and cohesion. The main part of sports psychology and psychological training helps teams to improve their cohesion. The more the team works as a whole, the better the results it shows.
5. Instill an effective belief system. One of the fields of sports psychology is helping athletes identify ineffective beliefs and attitudes. These beliefs need to be identified and replaced with new ways of thinking.
6. Develop self-confidence after injury. Some athletes are fully prepared physically to return to competition and training, but psychologically some scars remain. Injury can undermine self-confidence, raise doubts during competitions, and cause loss of attention.

From all that has been said. I conclude that sports should have sports psychologists, they need to be trained, and the attitude of sports functionaries towards psychology and psychologists in sports needs to be changed. It is necessary to form an understanding among coaches and athletes that psychological training is as necessary an element of athletic success as functional and technical training. And finally,

the main thing: sports psychology is not an academic discipline of the curriculum at the coaching faculties of physical education universities, but an applied field of psychological science and practice, which is of exceptional importance for studying the limits of human capabilities, ensuring the maximum realization of an athlete's functional fitness, preventing psychological breakdowns and personal injuries. A sports psychologist should be trained according to a special program and have the opportunity for internships. The practical activity of a sports psychologist should be licensed, but it is worth noting that sports psychology is not suitable for every athlete. Not every person involved in sports wants to "improve performance." Sports psychology is probably not for amateur athletes. That is, it is very important that the athlete himself wants to improve his psychological skills. Thus, psychological aspects are necessary for an athlete as well as constant physical training. Over time, the acquired psychological skills become an integral part of an athlete's life: he learns to focus on competitions without even noticing it.

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